

Effect of seedling age at transplanting on establishment, maturity, grain yield, and straw-grain ratio of 3 rice varieties, 1977-78 kharif, Allahabad, India.^a

Age of seedlings (days)	Establishment (DT)			Time between PE & maturity (days)			Maturity (days)			Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw-grain ratio		
	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S	B	R	S
25	6	6	6	35	48	50	109	128	130	2.7	2.6	2.4	1.18	1.26	1.19
35	5	5	5	30	45	35	117	130	132	2.0	2.8	2.8	1.31	1.30	1.42
45	5	5	5	28	40	37	120	133	135	2.0	1.9	2.1	1.26	1.26	1.37
55	5	4	4	22	30	31	131	135	141	0.8	0.8	1.3	1.21	1.19	1.21

^aDT = days after transplanting. B = Bala. R = Ratna. S = Sona. PE = panicle emergence. Grain yield: highly significant for seedling-age treatment. LSD for seedling-age treatments: 0.381. LSD for variety treatments: 0.258.

that were older at planting. In contrast, seedlings that were transplanted at an older age matured later. That could account for the greater setback at different growth stages of older seedlings. Relatively older seedlings of Ratna and Sona gave the highest grain yields when transplanted at 35 days but gave lower

yields when transplanted later. The straw-grain ratio, which was highest in 35-day-old seedlings, decreased in older seedlings, which grew and developed poorly.

It may be concluded that rice seedlings should be transplanted in alkali soils between the ages of 25 and 35 days. If

transplanted earlier, the seedlings may die; if transplanted later, they will yield poorly. The finding could be due to the higher concentration of soluble salts that results in the higher mortality of seedlings planted when between 21 and 25 days old. Thus, the older seedlings do better in saline alkali soils. ■

Potassium chloride pretreatment on rice seeds

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A field trial was conducted to determine the efficiency and response of rice seedlings to nutrients available in the soil. The variety ADT31 was used in a two-replication split-plot design.

The main plot treatments were M1 -- green leaf manure at 5 t/ha; M2 -- M1 + superphosphate at 250 kg/ha; M3 -- M2 + blue-green algae at 25 kg/ha; M4 -- nitrogen placed at 75 kg N/ha; and M5 -- control (no manure).

The subplot treatments were S1 --

Grain yield of fertilized rice plants and pretreated rice seeds. Tamil Nadu, India.

Main plot	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control	Subplot	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control
M1	3.6	116	S1	3.1	100
M2	3.7	120	S2	4.2	135
M3	3.5	114	S3	3.8	121
M4	4.2	134	S4	3.6	115
M5	3.1	100	S5	3.3	106
			S6	3.7	119
<i>'F' test</i>					
SE	122.0			45.1	
LSD	0.480			0.131	

control; S2 -- potassium chloride 1% (seed soaking); S3 -- manganese sulfate 8% (seed soaking); S4 -- ferrous sulfate 8% (seed soaking); S5 -- diammonium phosphate 4% (sprouted seed treatment); and S6 -- zinc sulfate 4% (sprouted seed treatment).

Among the main plot treatments, M4 gave a 34% higher yield than the control (see table).

Among the subplot treatments, S2 was significantly superior treatments and gave the highest grain yield, 35.0% over the control. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Performance of improved agricultural practices for dryland rice production in Sierra Leone

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Trials were conducted for the past 3 years on rice in farmers' fields under

dryland ecology at sites across Sierra Leone to determine:

1. If permanent cultivation can replace the bush fallow-rice system of traditional cultivation.
2. If improved cultivation methods can increase the yields of traditional rice varieties.
3. The benefit-cost ratio due to

fertilizer application.

Upland farmers in this part of Africa every year clear the bush from a new site and abandon that site after one rice crop or a crop of groundnut, cassava, or both, and return to the same site 8-10 years later. The fallow period has been reduced to 4-5 years in some parts of Sierra Leone.

Table 1. Average yield of rice (ROK 3) in uplands under different cropping systems. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1976 wet season.

Cropping system (no. of rice crops after bush fallow) ^a	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)		
		Without fertilizer	With fertilizer	
			60 kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha
1st	5	1.26	1.93	2.04
2d	4	0.77	1.87	2.05
3d	4	0.82	1.61	1.82

^aOne rice crop was grown per year.

Table 2. Effect of improved and traditional cultivation practices on the yield of a local rice variety. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1978 wet season.

District	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Yield increase (%) due to improved practices
		Improved practices	Traditional practices	
Kambia	5	1.82	0.90	101
Tonkolili	5	1.04	0.57	77
Bo	5	1.61	0.85	88
Moyamba	10	1.56	1.02	51
Kailahun	5	1.30	0.61	114
Kono	5	1.24	0.84	47

Table 3. Net returns on investment on fertilizer application to upland rice. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1978 wet season.^a

District	Net return (\$/\$1 investment)			
	60 kg N/ha	30 kg K/ha	60 kg N and 30 kg K/ha	60 kg N, 30 kg P, and 30 kg K/ha
Kambia	7.23	4.86	5.91	2.64
Bombali	3.63	7.94	4.90	5.38
Tonkolili	2.70	3.16	3.07	3.50
Kaoinadugu	3.30	7.80	0.78	0.71
Bo	1.87	5.39	1.05	1.07
Moyamba	7.00	20.35	8.81	5.09
Kailahun	4.41	26.92	6.37	3.01

^aPrice of 1 kg N = \$0.49, 1 kg P₂O₅ = \$0.70, 1 kg K₂O = \$0.25, and 1 kg rice grain = \$0.22.

In the first rice crop grown after bush fallow around Rokupr, the average rice yield with the application of 60–80 kg N/ha was 1.9–2.0 t/ha. The rice yield in the second and third year after bush fallow could be maintained at a similar level through the application of adequate amounts of fertilizers (Table 1). It is therefore not true that upland rice should not be grown in successive years on the same site.

The trials in farmers' fields to study the effect of improved practices included fertilizer application and line sowing. The results demonstrated that farmers' production with local varieties can be improved considerably through improved cultivation practices (Table 2).

The fertilizer response data collected from on-farm trials showed that investment on fertilizer was highly remunerative. Allowing for the risk of crop failures due to natural calamities and other costs in fertilizer application, a net profit of \$2 or more every \$1 investment can be considered remunerative (Table 3).

The results show that in the bush fallow-rice system, the application of either nitrogen or potassium, or both, gives high net returns in almost all districts. ■

Growth and yield of *Tilapia nilotica* fish and rice in irrigated paddies

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An experiment to determine the effect of two population densities (25,000 and 37,500) of *Tilapia nilotica* on the growth and yield of the fish as well as on rice yield was conducted in farmers' fields at

the BRRI Cropping Systems Research site at Salna in 1979 aus (Apr–Aug). The rice variety Chandina was transplanted with and without fish. Two trenches, each 1 m wide and 50 cm deep, were maintained across the middle of the paddies with fish. Well-prepared levees were maintained around the paddies. Fish were released into the field 5 days after transplanting (DT). Water depth was maintained at 5–10 cm until 25 DT and at 10–15 cm for the remainder of

the period.

The paddies without fish were kept flooded at a depth of 5–10 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 50 kg N/ha and 43 kg P₂O₅/ha. At 30 DT the water depth was reduced to about 2–4 cm, and nitrogen was topdressed.

The rice crop and the fish were harvested at 106 DT. The fish whose initial population was 25,000 increased 215% in number per hectare; each fish increased in size by 5 cm (see table). The

The influence of 2 population densities of fish on the number, size, and weight of fish and on rice yields. BRRI, 1979.

Population	Fish population (no./ha)			Fish size (cm)			Fish wt (kg/ha)			Rice yield (t/ha)	
	Initial	At harvest	Increase	Initial	At harvest	Increase	Initial	At harvest	Increase	With fish	Without fish
1	25,000	53,771	28,771	4.5	9.5	5.0	114	442	328	2.8	2.8
2	37,500	78,457	40,957	4.5	8.5	4.0	149	273	124	2.6	2.6
Mean	31,250	66,114	34,864	4.5	9.0	4.5	132	358	226	2.7	2.7